

***Macropsalliota tropica* is found in China**

Kun L. Yang (mugoture@gmail.com; College of Forestry and Landscape Architecture, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

Jia Y. Lin (mycofloscula@gmail.com; College of Plant Protection, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

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Text

In the ITS-nrLSU phylogeny inferred by Yang *et al.* (2024), the recently established genus *Macropsalliota* is unresolved with three separate subclades, namely *Imelegris*, *Itropica* and *Iamericana*, and members of *Iamericana* are common and thus already have *rpb2* and *tef-1a* data at that time. Soon after we got a collection of *Imelegris* with five loci sequenced (ITS, nrLSU, *rpb1*, *rpb2* & *tef-1a*) in the late 2024 (published in Yang *et al.* (2025)), our dream was changed to catch a *Itropica* collection in China ourselves for multilocus sequencing.

Macromorphologically, according to the basionymic protologue of *Macropsalliota tropica* (Dutta *et al.* 2021), this species could be understood as a *Candelolepiota sinica* with a more robust habit and a more distinct damaged coloration, or a *Macropsalliota melegris* directly turning reddish after damaged. *Candelolepiota sinica* is very common across our city, so we would never miss something looking like *Candelolepiota* but exhibiting even a slight morphological difference from then on. It's unexpected that the good luck came so quickly. One day in June, on the way to a shopping mall in Haizhu District at night, we noticed some unusual lepiotoid mushrooms growing on a lawn beside the road. They were of bad condition, had been nearly air-dried, looked like *C. sinica*, but the squamules on pileus were so flat and distinct (Figure 1, top right). Something related to *Imelegris*? We assumed, but still carried on efforts to find some more fresh basidiomata nearby, and fortunately we did find two (Figure 1, top left). God they directly turned reddish to brownish so quickly and distinct especially the stipe after touched! *Candelolepiota* and *Imelegris* would never act like this! Morphologically they should be *Macropsalliota tropica*, we comforted ourselves, and the sequencing results confirmed our point (Figure 2).

Thanks to our hopeful and careful attitude, we surprisingly found some other collections, originally thought as *Candelolepiota sinica*, but proven to be *Macropsalliota tropica* by sequences! This even led Kun L. Yang to suspect that some so-called "*Leucoagaricus lacrymans*" collections made in his childhood should actually be *M.*

tropica! However, of course, the difficulty on distinguishing *M. tropica* and *C. sinica* is still too much better than that on distinguishing *Agaricus andrewii* and *A. cantonotraminus* as earlier we discussed; and you may easily summarize the characters of their each based on figures 3 and 4.

▲ **Figure 1.** The two most impressed collections of *Macropsalliota tropica*. The bottom photo was taken in the shopping mall.

▲ **Figure 2.** Four-locus (ITS-nrLSU-*rpb2-tef-1a*) phylogeny of *Candelolepiota* and *Macropsalliota*. All our collections have four loci successfully sequenced.

▲ **Figure 3.** More collections of *Macropsalliota tropica*, some quite similar to *Candelolepiota sinica*.

▲ **Figure 4.** New collections of *Candelolepiota sinica* made in 2025 used for multilocus sequencing to explore infraspecific genetic variation.

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